

Christian Vision of Commitment to Protecting Creation Envisioned in *Laudate Deum*

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Abstract

Laudate Deum reminds us of our responsibilities towards our planet and invites us to acknowledge the biodiversity in the world created by God. In *Laudate Deum*, Pope Francis expresses his concern about anthropogenic climate change and calls for prompt action by those in positions of authority in communities and nations. His appeal is relevant in light of the current climate changes that most scientists acknowledge. He sets Christian principles as the foundation for an integral ecology, “care for our common home.” This article explores the Christian vision of the commitment to protect creation from the alarming environmental crisis.

Introduction

Laudate Deum, a short document by Pope Francis, a follow-up to his 2015 encyclical *Laudato Si'*, outlines his critique of the ineffectiveness of global institutions in addressing the devastating effects of climate change and urgently addresses global warming and climate change as a great call to action. His own words, “For when human beings claim to take God’s place, they become their own worst enemies,” (LD 73) summarize the central message of this apostolic exhortation. Pope Francis goes into battle with people who deny outright the severity of the threat posed by climate change.¹

In the final section of the apostolic exhortation, Pope Francis emphasizes “the spiritual motivations” of his approach that take his teaching beyond all ideologies and the pontiff seems to move away from fundamentalisms that reduce the current crisis solely to an ecological issue and also from irresponsible deniers who do not want to change anything in our current societies. The pope sets the foundation for what is characteristic of an ecology that is explicitly Christian. He is interacting with people of good will, but he is doing so from a Christian perspective. In choosing the

title “*Laudate Deum*”, he is putting God at the centre as the point of reference for all of our environmental concerns. Therefore, according to the Holy Father, it is important to stay grounded in God when dealing with these environmental concerns. The Pope explains the Christian vision of the commitment to protecting creation in the current context of environmental crisis. The foundation for his teachings on protecting creation stems from the first creation story in Genesis 1.

1. Intrinsic Value of the Non-human World

Pope Francis emphasizes that respect for nature must be based on God’s creative act, since the world is our ‘common home’ and a free gift from divine love. The Book of Genesis records that upon the creation of the universe God saw everything that he had made was very good (Gen 1:31) and this divine approval affirms the perfection and flawlessness of God’s creation. God is pre-eminently the one who is good, and his goodness is reflected in his works. God’s radiance is imbued into the creation, which bears witness to his greatness and goodness. The basis of respect for nature thus lies in God as its Creator.² The Pope reminds us that Francis of Assisi began his Canticle with the praise of God, and this praise due only to God is indispensable for the ecological sensitivity that should be part of the Christian tradition.³ To put it differently, the respect given to God as the Creator is linked to the respect for other creatures.

It is important for humans to respect the laws of nature and uphold the delicate harmony that exists among the creatures of this world. God brings humans and all of his creatures together, while the technocratic paradigm can keep us isolated from the world around us.⁴ Therefore, creatures’ disappearance from this world should not leave individuals and society unmoved. The Pope cites Lev 25:23, which states that nature is solely owned by God and cannot be sold for eternity. In reality, humans are only ‘aliens and tenants’ in this ‘shared home’ that was given to humanity by the Creator. Therefore, we are accountable for the world that is under God’s possession.

“There can be no ecology without an adequate anthropology”, said Pope Francis in *Laudato Si’* (LS 118). In *Laudate Deum*, key anthropological considerations are highlighted by the Pope. He stresses that genuine love for God’s creation necessitates a profound commitment to the common good. It is important that we don’t think of the non-human world only as a resource but as a divine gift. The common good requires the

dedicated protection of our environment, which is an integral part of it. The enslavement of both nature and ourselves is a result of losing sight of nature as a gift and a present from the Creator. Pope Francis cautions, “Everything that exists ceases to be a gift for which we should be thankful, esteem and cherish, and instead becomes a slave, prey to any whim of the human mind and its capacities” (LD 22).

The pope’s message highlights the importance of being concerned for God’s beloved creation, which is deeply rooted in the biblical notion of creation.⁵ Genesis story of creation introduces God, not just as the Creator, but also as the one who has a plan and purpose for mankind which involves a living in a relationship of obedience to God. The creation account in Gen 1 reveals the sovereignty of the God in the act of creation and since all that exists in the universe, including man, owe their existence to God, they are to be under the sovereign rule of the Creator. According to Gen 1, creation is the free act of God, based on his own wisdom and power, who formed the whole natural order through his word. All things in the universe are under the sovereign control of the God of Israel, who created it and everything within it. Furthermore, creation must be subject to the Creator. Since everything is created by a sovereign decision on the part of God every creation, including man, is dependent upon and is under the authority of the Creator.

Two fundamental reasons are mentioned by the Pope that reinforce the need to respect nature. First, loving God requires us to also love the universe he created. Second, because God wills and loves them, creatures have an intrinsic value that must be respected. Humans are unique and central among God’s creatures, but human life cannot be comprehended and sustainable without other creatures who are linked to us through unseen bonds. Humans are not omnipotent. In *Laudato Si’*, the Pope states that “Our insistence that each human being is an image of God should not make us overlook the fact that each creature has its own purpose. None is superfluous. The entire material universe speaks of God’s love, his boundless affection for us. Soil, water, mountains: everything is, as it were, a caress of God” (LS 84). Pope Francis is very close to the Theilhardian vision, which contemplates the evolution of the universe as a “Christogenesis.”⁶ God has created and loved the universe from the beginning, and it cannot be reduced to a pure natural order (cf. LS 100; LD 65).

2. A Sustainable Coexistence

The respect for nature is derived from a spirituality that recognizes humans as brothers and sisters in our interactions with other creatures in the universe. The Pope talks about the interconnectedness of humans and nature and how to maintain a sustainable coexistence. Humans play a crucial role in the universe's journey towards God's fullness. Francis urges us to participate in civic or political activities that place emphasis on dialogue and cooperation, and to reject all forms of violence that damage the social fabric and the world, the preservation of which is essential for a meaningful life.

Love towards God is the catalyst for loving creatures instead of hampering them, and loving our neighbour naturally extends to them. The Pope is arguing for sustainable resource management and protection of the ecosystem by strengthening the Gospel law of love. This love must be extended to our relationships with creatures. This mysticism requires a profound respect for life in all its forms, including promoting animal welfare, protecting ecosystems, and ensuring equity in resource distribution. To put it another way, loving ourselves as human beings today means taking action for future generations to ensure that they can flourish in a healthy and prosperous environment.

Francis holds anthropocentrism to be a symbol of humans' obligation to care for the world and environment, and his idea of anthropocentrism is in opposition to the anthropocentrism promoted by the technocratic paradigm. The technocratic paradigm holds that humans are the owners of the world and can change it at their own discretion using their techno-scientific knowledge.⁷ Human interference in nature, as stated by the Pope, destroys the planet and all forms of life regardless of our certainty about the role of humans in climate change.

It is clear that Pope Francis' anthropocentrism aims to prevent an excessive separation between humans and nature. The point is to re-evaluate how we use the power that technology has given us. Taking into account the significance of scientific knowledge and its progress, it is not possible to assume that technology has no limits and that nature is the property of humans. Living in harmony with the world and its elements, including ourselves, is both possible and desirable.

It is certain that separating human beings from the rest of creation will hold back the harmonious development of respectful human life in concert with the environment. Human beings, says the Pope "must be

recognized as a part of nature. Human life, intelligence, and freedom are elements of nature that enrich our planet, as they are part of its internal workings and equilibrium” (LD 26). In order to achieve a sustainable coexistence, it is crucial to seek a more balanced and integral approach that acknowledges the interconnectedness of humans and nature. This is the Christian spirituality that the pope seeks to promote in the present context of the ecological crisis.

The Pope not only affirms the interconnectedness of all the elements of the earth to the extent that God has united us indissolubly with all creatures, but also insists on the consequences of this principle—the fact that everything is connected affects the way we act. By adopting this holistic principle that governs true integral ecology, humans can avoid acting violently that separates them from the rest of creation.

3. Humans are Custodians of Creation

The ecological sensitivity promoted by the pope is rooted in a ‘situated anthropocentrism’ which the Christian tradition cannot ever abandon. The pope explains the anthropocentrism of his perspective clearly, in line with the Judeo-Christian tradition, where the human being play a unique and central role in the created world. It is true that this is a “situated anthropocentrism” because human life is not possible without other creatures.

The Judeo-Christian worldview insists on the special and central value of man in the midst of the wonderful concert of all living beings, but today we are forced to recognize that one can only speak of a “situated anthropocentrism.” That is, we must acknowledge that human life cannot be understood or sustained without other living beings” (LD 67).⁸

The duty of human beings is to be the custodians of creation and guide all things towards their ultimate fulfilment; everyone has the responsibility to care for creation. Furthermore, there is no way to give the world a higher value than that which is given to it by God, since no one can ascribe a higher value to creation than God Himself. The importance of creatures, which come from God’s love, appears to be the most complete foundation of all the concerns we must have for ecology.

It is important to note how Pope Francis rejects the “technocratic paradigm that underlies the current process of environmental decay” (LD 20).⁹ In the technocratic approach, the emphasis is on absolute dominance

and control over nature. The first issue with this perspective is that it forces humans to assume the role of the creator themselves. He writes: “We have made impressive and awesome technological advances, and we have not realized that at the same time we have turned into highly dangerous beings, capable of threatening the lives of many beings and our own survival” (LD 28). The determinism of technocratic scientism leads people to believe that they are capable of knowing, predicting, and transforming the world at will. In paragraph 27 of *Laudate Deum* the Pope affirms:

For this reason, a healthy ecology is also the result of interaction between human beings and the environment, as occurs in the indigenous cultures and has occurred for centuries in different regions of the earth. Human groupings have often “created” an environment, reshaping it in some way without destroying it or endangering it. The great present-day problem is that the technocratic paradigm has destroyed that healthy and harmonious relationship. In any event, the indispensable need to move beyond that paradigm, so damaging and destructive, will not be found in a denial of the human being, but include the interaction of natural systems “with social systems”.

The choice of ‘*Laudato Deum*’ as the title of Pope Francis’ exhortation appears to be deliberate. The Christian view holds that the world is a free gift from God. By placing God at the centre, it is possible to foster an experience similar to that lived by St. Francis of Assisi and to that described in the Gospels. We are compelled by this mystical experience to live on this earth with respect for the creatures we share a common home with. Realizing that this free gift from God requires us to act as stewards of creation, rather than trying to manipulate or exploit it without limits.

The Holy Father’s teaching about the responsibilities of humans as custodians of creation is similar to Genesis’ understanding of their role. Genesis 1:26 begins by stating man’s relationship to the Creator and then proceeds to explain man’s relationship to the rest of the creation: “... and let them have dominion over the fish of the sea, and over the birds of the air, and over the cattle, and over all the wild animals of the earth, and over every creeping thing that creeps upon the earth” (Gen 1:28). Man is created to exercise dominion over all other living creatures; he is meant to rule the animal world. But this rule is intended to be compassionate and not exploitative. Man has been given the task of subduing the earth and governing the animals of the sky, land, and water. However, this power

comes with a responsibility. Humans have a superior position that requires them to be responsible for the rest of creation.¹⁰ In relation to the creator, human beings stand as representatives of the rest of the creation and they praise and thank the creator for the entire creation.

It is our duty as humans to both contemplate creation and act as faithful stewards, protecting the environment for our own and all creatures' well-being. Our unique position in the creation necessitates a special responsibility towards the whole creation. This obligation demands that we accept the concept of 'situated anthropocentrism', which transforms our relationships with God, our fellow humans, and the rest of creation.

Conclusion

Averting looming disasters in both nature and human society requires a paradigm shift and practical strategies. In the world we live in, only human beings have the freedom to love or destroy nature. Our societies are the ones who have the power to decide on our way of life, and the future of the world relies on this fundamental choice that human beings have to make. It is in this sense that humans occupy the centre of nature. It is important to frame this anthropocentric viewpoint in a context that encourages us to value and respect all creatures in the universe that were created by God and are not ours. The pope's call for a more contemplative change in our lifestyle is based on a profoundly Christian and Bible-based perspective to preserve our planet. His appeal is clearly relevant in light of the current climate changes that are acknowledged by most scientists.

Pope Francis expresses his concern about anthropogenic climate change and calls for prompt action to be taken by those in positions of authority in communities and nations. Approaching *Laudate Deum* from the perspective of enhancing our reverence for and care for creation will assist everyone in taking responsibility for the environment. The interaction between humans and the environment is essential for creating a healthy ecology. He warns that the power of scientific knowledge and its progress are turning against us and urges us to recognize the 'inexhaustible richness' of God's creation (LD 63). Concretely, *Laudate Deum* reminds us of our responsibilities towards our planet and invites us to acknowledge the biodiversity in the world created by God.

About the Author

Mathew Olickal, MCBS obtained his master's degree in English, license (LSS) and doctorate (DSS) in Sacred Scripture from Studium Biblicum Franciscanum in Jerusalem, Israel. He has written numerous articles and books. He is teaching Bible at many institutes in India. He was the Rector and President of MCBS Sanathana Divyakarunya Vidyapeetham in Thamarassery, Kerala. Currently, he is the Provincial of MCBS Zion Province in Kozhikode.

¹ Andreas Gonçalves Lind's article, titled "Laudate Deum - Ecology in the Light of the Gospel", published in *La Civiltà Cattolica*, on their website (<https://www.laciviltacattolica.com/laudate-deum-ecology-in-the-light-of-the-gospel/#>, December 8, 2023) was a great help in writing this article.

² Four images of God are presented in Gen 1-3: God as Creator (Gen 1), as Lawgiver (Gen 2:17), as Judge (Gen 3), and as Saviour (Gen 3:15).

³ The Genesis account of creation differs markedly from the other Near Eastern cosmogonies in its postulation of monotheism: There is only a single Creator who is Yahweh, and no other gods are involved in the process of creation. No other gods or goddesses participated in the process of creation either as helpers or as opponent. The pagan concept of procreation for the creative process is completely absent in Genesis.

⁴ Technocratic paradigm is the technocratic approach that leads us into thinking we can become powerful and wise enough to apply our power to all things. Pope Francis is critical of the technocratic paradigm for its tendency to distort our perception of reality and consequently lead us to make both moral and technical mistakes in our interactions with the world (cf. *LD*, 101). The technocratic paradigm is not about the technologies themselves, but rather about an ideology called throwaway culture, which is actually part of the wider culture of death.

⁵ The book of Genesis, particularly the primeval history, portrays God as the creator of all things, including time and space. The way the world functions is shaped by him to achieve his aims for the planet and its inhabitants.

⁶ Teilhard developed an original Christology as part of his evolutionary cosmological vision, who speaks of the dynamic of divine love that links the act of creation with that of incarnation and redemption. His primary objective was to make the person of Christ the focal point of cosmic evolution. From the start of his writing, he mentioned the universal Christ and how the cosmos was centred around him. Cf. Pierre Teilhard de Chardin, *La mia fede: Scritti teologici*, Brescia 1993, 173.

⁷ Cf. Gonçalves Lind, 'Laudate Deum', <https://www.laciviltacattolica.com/laudate-deum-ecology-in-the-light-of-the-gospel/#>.

⁸ In *Laudato Si*, the Pope acknowledges the existence of a middle ground between the extremes of ‘false biocentrism’ and ‘misguided anthropocentrism’ (LS 128), although there is no term to describe it. He employs the concept of ‘situated anthropocentrism’ in *Laudate Deum*.

⁹ The danger of technocracy has always been a concern for Popes. John XXIII in *Pacem in Terris* (1963) issued a warning against the danger of nuclear weapons; John Paul II in *Centesimus Annus* (1991), Pope Benedict XVI in *Caritas in Veritate* (2009), and Pope Francis in *Laudato Si’* (2015) emphasized the dangers of technology’s overdependence, particularly when it comes to threats to the environment. In today’s world, it is common for us to believe that technology is everything, capable of doing everything, and can solve everything.

¹⁰ The first creation story reaches its climax with the creation of man. The earth, man’s home, is prepared and everything is ready for arrival of God’s masterpiece of creation, namely, man. The narrative proceeds in such a way that it emphasises the significance man. The unique traits that make the creation of man particularly remarkable and special are two: (a) the announcement “let us make man” and (b) the declaration that man is made in God’s own image and likeness.